

Blockchain-Based Decentralized Health Record Management

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ABSTRACT The healthcare industry has been adopting innovative technologies that allow digitalization of health records and automation of clinical processes. The need for interoperability across different departments in healthcare requires a seamless data exchange inside the system. However, confidentiality and integrity of data are critical issues during the process of sharing data across different authorized parties. Electronic Health Records (EHRs) are electronically-stored health information in a digital format. EHRs are typically shared among healthcare stakeholders and face power failure, data misuse, lack of privacy, security, and audit trail. On the other hand, blockchain is the revolutionary invention of the twentieth century that offers a distributed and decentralized setting to communicate among nodes in a list of networks without a central authority. Blockchain have been an interesting research area for a long time and the benefits it provides have been used by a number of various industries. Similarly, the healthcare sector stands to benefit immensely from the blockchain technology due to security, privacy, confidentiality and decentralization. Nevertheless, the Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems face problems regarding data security, integrity and management. In this paper, we discuss how the blockchain technology can be used to transform the EHR systems and could be a solution of these issues. We present a framework that could be used for the implementation of blockchain technology in healthcare sector for EHR. The aim of our proposed framework is firstly to implement blockchain technology for EHR and secondly to provide secure storage of electronic records by defining granular access rules for the users of the proposed framework. Moreover, this framework also discusses the scalability problem faced by the blockchain technology in general via use of off-chain storage of the records. This framework provides the EHR system with the benefits of having a scalable, secure and integral blockchain-based solution.

KEYWORDS Blockchain, health records, electronic health records, decentralization, and scalability.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the evolution of the Internet of Things (IoT) and abundance of health devices and health apps, a vast amount of medical data are recorded and transferred every day.

This large database of medical information needs management regarding privacy, security, and availability. Hospitals and doctors need to access to the patient's medical information during the treatment process while ensuring security and privacy of sensitive information of patients as they share them with hospitals and medical institutes. The recent advent in technology

is affecting all parts of human life and is changing the way we use and perceive things previously. Just like the changes technology has offered in various other sectors of life, it is also finding new ways for improvement in healthcare sector. The main benefits that advancement in technology is offering are to improve security, user experience and other aspects of healthcare sector. These benefits were offered by Electronic Health Record (EHR) and Electronic Medical Record (EMR) systems. However, they still face some issues regarding the security of medical

records, user ownership of data, data integrity etc. The solution to these issues could be the use of a novel technology, i.e., Blockchain. This technology offers to provide a secure, temper-proof platform for storing medical records and other healthcare related information. Blockchain Technology introduced a financial application that has started a revolution in many fields including healthcare information systems. Blockchain technology can provide a solution that not only helps to secure recording and sharing of medical records but also to assure the privacy of each patient's data by giving their medical data ownership to the patients, themselves.

This paper is organized as follows the section II of this paper summarizes the basics of blockchain technology and its dependencies; section III narrates the related work done in this domain. The section IV explains the design and architecture of the proposed framework and section V explains the performance of this framework. The last section provides the conclusion and references.

II. BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY AND ITS DEPENDENCIES

Blockchain is a chain of blocks that are connected together and are continuously growing by storing transactions on the blocks. This platform uses a decentralized approach that allows the information to be distributed and that each piece of distributed information or commonly known as data have shared ownership. Blockchains holds batches of

transactions that are hashed thus providing them security and they are managed by peer-to-peer networks. A blockchain has certain benefits such as security, anonymity, and integrity of data with no third party intervention. These benefits make it a reasonable choice to store patient's medical records on it, because the innovation of technology in the healthcare industry has made the security of patient's medical data a top priority. A number of researchers have also identified that using blockchain technology in healthcare would be a feasible solution.

This technology was introduced by Nakamoto, for his popular work of digital currency or crypto-currency, i.e., bitcoin. Nakamoto used blockchain technology to solve the double spending problem of bitcoin but soon this novel technology was being used in many other applications.

How Bitcoin Blockchain Works

There are two challenges of the transaction system without central control agency: (1) single point of failure and (2) peer-to-peer double spending of the same digital asset like money. Blockchain technology solves this problem using two mechanisms: hash-chain time-stamping and proof of work algorithm. First, in order to verify each transaction, it should be stored in each computation node in the network. All transactions are timestamped and distributed in the network. Bitcoin blockchain exploits hash-chain as distributed timestamp mechanism to determine the possibility of doing the transaction and maintaining a copy of

transaction chain in every node. Second, bitcoin blockchain uses the reward and punishment mechanism for preventing any possible interruption or malicious transaction. Miners are the participants who do the mining process in blockchain, i.e., creating new blocks with enclosed transactions list and chaining them to the previous blocks. Figure.1 shows how blocks are created and chained together. Each block has two important parts: (1) Content: a validated list of transactions. The transacted digital asset can be digital money (e.g., Bitcoin, Ethereum) or any kind of data such as a school diploma, a medical record. (2) Header: which includes metadata, such as (a) Block reference number to the content of the block, known as the hash root, (b) The time the block was created known as timestamp, (c) A link back to the previous block, and (d) A random number (nonce) which is added to the block address according to the proof of work algorithm.

In bitcoin blockchain system miners use proof of work protocol in order to find a new address for the new block with specific properties. This property in bitcoin blockchain is a 32-bit crypto number with seventeen zero bit in the beginning. Miners run this algorithm multiple times to get such a number by trying different random numbers (nonce). After finding a new address for the new block, the miner updates the ledger and send it to the entire network. Then the majority of the network should confirm the new block. This process is called proof of work or consensus in bitcoin blockchain system. The mining process is difficult, time taking and costly,

this prevents creating invalid and fraud transactions. Therefore, bitcoin mechanism provides rewards for the miner who can add the new block first, as an incentive to compensate the efforts and cost associated with the mining process. Another benefit of using proof of work consensus protocol is that it let blockchain to be immutable audit trails by chaining blocks together using a hash function. Each block contains the hash value of the previous block's header (Prev.Hash), and therefore if an attacker tries to modify a block, all the upcoming blocks should be modified. Such a modification needs a high computation power, time and cost. Even if the attacker succeeds to create the fraud chain of blocks, replacing it with the honest chain requires the consensus of the majority of the nodes in the network. Thus, the bitcoin blockchain system is highly secure against any modification and failure, and this comes from its specific structure.

Blockchain Technology for Other

Sectors

Although blockchain was first introduced for finance, there are many other applications, which has been developed and implemented. Blockchain technology, as a horizontal technology, is revolutionizing the future of the transactionbased exchange in different industries such as finance, insurance, telecommunication, and healthcare.

According to Melanie Swan, there are three phases of blockchain adoption: Blockchain 1.0 is the first development of blockchain as a cryptocurrency, bitcoin. Blockchain 2.0 refers to smart contracts, financial

records and tracking the ownership of the properties inside the blockchain system. Blockchain 3.0 will come in science, medicine, and education.

Blockchain Technology for Healthcare

The idea of applying blockchain in healthcare comes out of the need for security and interoperability in healthcare. With the evolution of IoT and abundance of health devices and mobile healthcare applications, a considerable amount of medical data are recorded and transferred every day. This data traffic needs management regarding privacy and security. Blockchain technology can provide a solution that not only helps to secure recording and sharing of medical records but also assures the privacy of each patient's data by giving the patients, their medical data ownership. Besides the advantages of blockchain for healthcare management, its challenges should be met in advance

KEY FEATURES OF BLOCKCHAIN

1) DECENTRALIZATION

With blockchain the information is distributed across the network rather than at one central point. This also makes the control of information to be distributed and handled by consensus reached upon by shared input from the nodes connected on the network. The data that was before concentrated at one central point is now handled by many trusted entities.

2) DATA TRANSPARENCY

Achieving data transparency in any technology is to have a trust based

relationship between entities. The data or record at stake should be secured and temper proof. Any data being stored on the blockchain is not concentrated at one place and is not controlled by one node but is instead distributed across the network. The ownership of data is now shared and this makes it to be transparent and secure from any third party intervention.

3) SECURITY AND PRIVACY

Blockchain technology uses cryptographic functions to provide security to the nodes connected on its network. It uses SHA-256 cryptographic algorithm on the hashes that are stored on the blocks. SHA stands for *Secure Hashing Algorithm*, these hashes provide security to the blockchain as data integrity is ensured by them. Cryptographic hashes are strong one way functions that generate checksum for digital data that cannot be used for data extraction. This makes blockchain as such a decentralized platform made secure by the cryptographic approaches which makes it to be a good option for privacy protection of certain applications.

III. RELATED WORK

Blockchain technology was designed by Nakamoto [13], the basic idea was to have a cryptographically secured and a decentralized currency that would be helpful for financial transactions. Eventually, this idea of blockchain was being used in various other fields of life; healthcare sector also being one of them intends to use it. A number of researchers have carried out the research on this area,

these research works focus on the fact that whether the idea of using blockchain for healthcare sector is feasible or not. They also identify the advantages, threats, problems or challenges associated by the usage of this technology. Some researchers also discussed the challenges that would be faced while actually implementing this on a larger scale.

A. THEORETICAL/ANALYTICAL BLOCKCHAIN-BASED RESEARCH

Gordon and Catalini, conducted a study that focused on the methods by which blockchain technology would facilitate the healthcare sector. They identified, that healthcare sector is controlled by hospitals, pharmaceutical companies and other involved third parties. They specified data sharing as the key reason why blockchains should be used in healthcare. This study also identified four factors or approaches due to which healthcare sector needs to transform for usage of blockchain technology. These include way for dealing of digital access rights, data availability, and faster access to clinical records and patient identity. It also discusses the on-chain and offchain storage of data. The study also included the challenges or barriers faced by usage of blockchain technology these were huge volume of clinical records, security and privacy, patient engagement.

Vujičić *et al.*, presented an overview of blockchain technology, bitcoin and Ethereum. The authors define that information technology landscape is constantly changing and blockchain technology is benefiting the information systems. They explained bitcoin as a peer-to-peer distributed network used for performing bitcoin transactions. They also defined that proof-of-work consensus algorithm along with the mining of blockchain concept. The authors emphasize on the fact that scalability is a severe problem faced by blockchain

and that certain solutions are proposed for solution of scalability problem these include SegWit and Lightning, Bitcoin Cash and Bitcoin Gold. The paper also explained Ethereum and its dependencies and it also differentiates Ethereum blockchain from bitcoins' blockchain.

Wang *et al.*, conducted a study that focused on smart contracts and its application in blockchain technology. They first introduce the smart contracts, their working framework, operating systems and other important concepts attached with them. The authors also discuss that how could smart contracts be used for the new concept of parallel blockchains. They identify that reason of using smart contracts in blockchain is due to the decentralization that is offered through the programming language code written in them. After introducing the basics of smart contract the author explained the various layers of blockchain that combine together to keep system functioning. These layers are data, network, consensus, incentive, contract, and application layer. The paper not only discusses the architecture and framework followed by smart contracts but it also gives an insight on its applications and challenges. The paper also discusses an important future trend of parallel blockchain that intends to create such blockchain that can optimize two different but important modules.

Kuo *et al.*, conducted a review that discussed several applications of blockchain in biomedical and healthcare sector. The authors identified that using blockchains for this domain offers many advantages and some of these are decentralization, persistence of clinical or medical records, data pedigree, and continuous accessibility to data and lastly secure information being accessible to biomedical or healthcare stakeholders. The limitations of blockchain technology were identified to be, confidentiality, speed, scalability

and threat of malicious attack, i.e., 51% attack. The authors identified these limitations to be critical for healthcare or biomedical sector as they are being used to store sensitive medical or clinical records. The solution to these problems were presented by authors to store sensitive medical data offchain, encryption of data to ensure confidentiality, and lastly to use VPNs (Virtual Private Networks) to ensure safety from malicious attacks.

B. PROTOTYPE/IMPLEMENTATION BLOCKCHAIN-BASED RESEARCH

Sahoo and Baruah, proposed a scalable framework of blockchain using Hadoop database. In order to solve the scalability problem of blockchain, they proposed to use the scalability provided by the underlying Hadoop database along with the decentralization provided by the blockchain technology. They used the method to store blocks on the Hadoop database, the blockchain on top of this framework includes all of the needed dependencies of blockchain but the blocks are stored on Hadoop database to improve scalability of the blockchain technology. To tackle the scalability problem of blockchain platform this study offers to use Hadoop database system, along with SHA3-256 for hashing used for transactions and blocks. The programming language used for this architecture was Java. This study, was helpful in understanding that blockchain can be used with other platforms that are scalable to improve or solve the scalability of this platform.

Zhang *et al.*, proposed a scalable solution to the blockchain for clinical records. The basic aim of this study was to design such an architecture that complies with the Office of National Coordinator for Health Information Technology (ONC) requirements. This study identified the barriers that this technology faces mainly include concerns related to privacy, security of blockchain, and scalability problems related to huge volume of

datasets being transmitted on this platform, and lastly there is no universal standard enforced for data being exchanged on blockchain. This study also include a demonstration of a decentralized application (DAPP) based on the design formulated on the ONC requirements as mentioned before. They also included the lessons learnt and how can FHIR chain be improved.

Kim *et al* proposed a system for management of medical questionnaires and the aim of this system is data sharing through blockchain technology. The authors explain that selection of data storage and sharing of medical questionnaire is to use this data for further medical and clinical research purposes. They emphasized that it would be helpful for developing diagnosis system, resolving terminologies being used in EHR systems and security issues associated with these systems was also a reason due to which authors selected blockchain technology for their proposed framework. This study contains two main functions, i.e., to create, store the data gathered by questionnaires and to share that data. Another benefit proposed by the system is the validation of the questionnaire being submitted in the system. The questionnaires that are added on this system are first validated to be correct specified format and then are parsed to differentiate the personal data and specific data related to questionnaire results. This would ensure that data could be shared for future research purposes. The authors also address the scenario when a third party requests to access this questionnaire data, this would need the patients' permission that is asked by the doctor to let third party view that data.

IV. SYSTEM DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE

The related work section includes the work done in the domain of health care being implemented using blockchain technology. As mentioned they

provided certain solutions for solving the prevalent problems in blockchain technology. The studies in discussion were mainly addressing the problems of scalability and data sharing through blockchain. They propose the solution of using an underlying database, pertaining to some ONC requirements and any other defined standards to solve them. In contrast to those solutions our proposed framework offers to solve this problem of scalability by using off-chain scaling mechanism of IPFS. Moreover, Ethereum is used for the overall implementation of the proposed framework. Ethereum and its dependencies are also discussed in the previous sections of this paper.

A. SYSTEM DESIGN

System design is the most important and vital part of any framework as it is used for the development of the system from its theory. This section includes the modules, architecture and various elements that are combined together to form the whole system's framework. As defined earlier the purpose behind this proposed framework is to create such a decentralized system that is temper-proof, secure and confidential blockchain-based system for electronic health records.

As visible in below figure 2, the proposed framework or system has three entities or modules. These modules when combined together would keep our system working. These entities or modules have further concepts that need to be understood they are explained as follows.

The proposed framework consists of users that could be patients, doctors, administration and nursing staff. They were given granular access as they should have varying level of authority on the system.

1) USER LAYER

A user of a system is defined as an individual who makes effective use of the system and its

resources. A user has various roles and features on the system, making him identifiable on the system. The users of this system could be patients, doctors and administrative staff etc. The main task of these users would be to interact with the system and perform basic tasks such as create, read, update and delete the medical records. The users using this system would be accessing the system's functionality by a browser which in technical terms we refer as DApp browser, as it is containing the GUI (Graphical User Interface) of the DApp, i.e., our proposed system framework. The GUI contains all the functions that could be accessed by a particular user. The user according to the assigned role could use this GUI for interacting with the other layer of the system, i.e., blockchain layer

2) BLOCKCHAIN LAYER

The next layer on the system is the blockchain layer; this layer contains the code or mechanism for interaction of user with the DApp which is functioning on the blockchain. This layer contains three elements inside it. They are:

- **Blockchain Assets:** In Ethereum blockchain, transaction is the process by which external user can update the state of the record or information stored on the Ethereum blockchain network. These transactions are treated as *assets* by the Ethereum blockchain as they are piece of information that user can send to another user or to simply store it for using it later.
- **Governance Rules:** Blockchain technology in general follows some consensus rules for its transactions to be done and computed. For this purpose it needs some consensus algorithms to keep the blockchain temper-proof and secure. Ethereum blockchain uses Proof of Work (PoW) consensus algorithm, the reason behind using it is also for ensuring that *governance* of

blockchain is maintained in a trusted manner which is through consent from all the trusted nodes attached to the blockchain network.

- **Network:** Ethereum blockchain uses the peer-to-peer network. In this network all the nodes are connected as *peers*. With no node acting as the central node controlling all the functions of the network. The reason behind using this network was because the idea was to create a distributed platform not a centralized. So, using a network where all the connected nodes have equal status and right was the best choice this technology could have done.

TRANSACTION

The system includes following transactions:

- **Add records** would create patient's medical records in the DApp. It contains the fields of ID, name, co-morbid, blood group, and IPFS hash. The patient's basic medical records is stored along with the IPFS hash that contains the file uploaded containing the lab results or other medical records of patient.
- **Update records** would update the medical records of patient. This can only change the basic information of the patient not the IPFS hash. IPFS hash is non-updateable to ensure security of records.
- **View records** would let the user view the medical records of a patient stored in DApp. The view records function is used both by doctors and patients. The patient can view his records by the system authenticating that patient views only his own medical records. For this purpose system uses the public account address of the patient to ensure that only the relevant medical records is shown to the patient.

- **Delete records** would make the user be able to delete record of any patient. The user here would be the doctors they are given this right to delete any patient's record stored on the blockchain.
- **Grant access** for each of the above mentioned transactions, certain user would need to have access to them, i.e., only the doctor or nursing staff can make changes in the records of the patient or add them. So, add and update records would only be accessible to these entities. Moreover, patient can view his medical records but won't be given the access to add or update them.

3) SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

As already explained in the previous sections, the system was implemented by using the Ethereum and its dependencies. This section explores system implementation in more detail to get an insight on the system various functions.

4) SMART CONTRACTS

As explained earlier, smart contracts are an important part of DApps as they are used for performing basic operations. Following contracts are included in this framework:

- Patient Records
- Roles

These contracts are used for giving access to the users on the DApp and performing CRUD operations on the records of patient. The *Patient Records* smart contract is made purely for implementing the functionality of the proposed framework.

It performs the CRUD operations along with the defining roles for access of these functions.

The second contract mentioned above, i.e., *Roles* is a predefined smart contract by the Open Zeppelin smart contract library. This library contains several smart contracts performing various functionalities

that could be used for creating our own smart contracts. The reason behind using this library was to make use of the benefits it provides, i.e., tested and community reviewed code. The *Roles* smart contract belongs to the Asset library, which is a sub-library of the Open Zeppelin library. The asset library contains various other contracts for defining the access rules but roles library provide a granular role definition mechanism which was the main reason behind selection of this smart contract.

The algorithm for defining the *Patient Records* smart contract is given below. It defines all the operations that are being performed in it and various conditions that are associated with them. It also explains how the *roles* are being maintained for granting access to a particular functionality.

V. PERFORMANCE

In this section we evaluate the performance of the proposed framework. By assessing the performance we can mitigate the risks associated with this novel technology that is understandable by very few individuals.

A. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

For testing performance of the proposed framework we have conducted experiments by using the following configurations:

- Intel Core i7-6498DU CPU @ 2.50GHz 2.60 GHz processor
- And 8.00 GB of memory with Windows 64-bit OS (version 10)

We developed our proposed framework by using the Solidity which is programming language of Ethereum. JavaScript and Python are encapsulated in the Solidity language which is provided by the Ethereum to write code in smart contracts.

1) TRANSACTION DATA

To evaluate the performance of the proposed framework following transaction data with its details are used.

- **Transaction Deployment Time (t_{x1})**

It is defined as the time when transaction gets deployed. In Ethereum, a smart contract is deployed using the transaction so this deployment time refers to that time.

- **Transaction Completion Time (t_{x2})**

It is defined as the time when the transaction is completed and confirmed by the blockchain which in this case is Ethereum.

2) EVALUATION METRICS

The metrics used for evaluation include the execution time, latency and throughput of the proposed framework. These are explained briefly as follows:

- **Execution Time** is defined as time duration (in seconds) between the transaction confirmation and its execution in the blockchain network. Mathematically, it is $(\max(t_{x2}) - \min(t_{x1}))$.
- **Throughput** refers to the amount of data that could be transferred from one location to another in a unit amount of time.
- **Latency** is known as the delay that occurs when a system component is waiting for another component of the system to respond to an action. In terms of time it could be referred as the difference of deployment and completion time of transaction.

C. RESULTS

1) PERFORMANCE ASSESMENT

In order to understand how our proposed framework would perform in real-case scenario of various users performing different functions on the framework we conducted

performance evaluation using Apache JMeter version 5.1.1 and Apache Version 2.00. Apache JMeter is a desktop performance testing tool which is used for analysis and testing of applications.

a: AVERAGE EXECUTION TIME

The execution time increases with the number of transactions being increased. These transactions are performed for the various functions that are included in the smart contract whose algorithm is defined in Section V. When there is only one user using the system the functions *Assign Roles*, *Add Patient Records* and *View Patient Records* would take 18.29 sec, 1 min 48 sec and 50 sec respectively for these functions to be executed. This time would increase when 100 users are using the system simultaneously.

b: THROUGHPUT

Algorithm 1 explains various functions that are included in the smart contract of the proposed framework. By using JMeter we simulated number of users from 100 users to 500 users (with period of 10 to 35), who are using the system and performing its various functions. In JMeter the throughput is represented in Data/time i.e. KB/sec units. While conducting the experiments we simulated the number of users as specified above and evaluated the performance of the system. These simulations are run on the proposed framework and at the end throughput is analyzed.

The following figure 4 shows the throughput of the proposed framework.

It is observed while conducting this experiment that as the number of users and requests increase the throughput of the system increased considerably in a linear manner.

c: AVERAGE LATENCY

Latency as defined earlier is the delay or difference in time when one system component sends a request and a response is generated by any other system component. The difference between these two actions is defined as latency. Here we have evaluated the average latency of the proposed framework by using JMeter. While evaluating the latency of the proposed framework we simulated the number of users by JMeter. In JMeter latency is measured in terms of milliseconds.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we discussed how blockchain technology can be useful for healthcare sector and how can it be used for electronic health records. Despite the advancement in healthcare sector and technological innovation in EHR systems they still faced some issues that were addressed by this novel technology, i.e., blockchain. Our proposed framework is a combination of secure record storage along with the granular access rules for those records. It creates such a system that is easier for the users to use and understand. Also, the framework proposes measures to ensure the system tackles the problem of data storage as it utilizes the off-chain storage mechanism of IPFS. And the role-based access also benefits the system as the medical records are only available to the trusted and related individuals. This also solves the problem of information asymmetry of EHR system.

For the future, we plan to implement the payment module in the existing framework. For this we need to have certain considerations as we need to decide how much a patient would pay for consultation by the doctor on this decentralized system functioning on the blockchain. We would also need to define certain policies and rules that comply with the principles of the healthcare sector.

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